
Descriptive Study of Badian Fishermen's *Dayang-Dayang* Form of Fishing for Folk Dancing

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Abstract

Folk dance is an epitome of expressing one's culture, livelihood, and beliefs. Dances that mirror the customs and traditions of people are as important as knowing the roots of one's identity. With an archipelagic country such as the Philippines, fishing livelihoods as expressions of culture can be a reference for folk dancing. However, through the test of time and unavailability of resources with lesser numbers of people performing, dance enthusiasts become less interested in pursuing their passion. Preservation of culture through folk dance is one way, a key of being a responsible citizen in cultivating the country's identity. Hence, the researchers with this study in Badian, Cebu, Philippines seek to document and uncover the rich culture of the municipality when it comes to indigenous fishing livelihood that present cultural abundance of artistry and ingenuity. It also aimed to show the Badiananons' prevailing cultural values specifically in ways of unique fishing through delving into the nature, background, characteristics, and movement patterns of "dayang-dayang" fishing style. This results in an increased awareness of one's identity through culture exploration. This paper also presents the basic dance steps, time signature, costume, and props that serves as dance literature for reference in future dance research. With that, this study suggests a creation of choreography and good musical accompaniment that will potentially expose the uniqueness of the fishing style through the art of dance in public performances and allow integration with teaching in physical education be possible.

Keywords: *Descriptive Study, Badian Fishermen, Dayang-Dayang Fishing, Folk Dancing*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is tagged as "the pearl of the orient seas" for the richness of its natural resources, culture, and traditions. Apparent to its these are the costumes, music, and dances. According to Hofelina (2019), Philippine folk dances and traditional dances depict the country's tradition, customs, and way of life. It mainly seeks to showcase cultural expressions through dancing in its pure and authentic form and upgrade cultural values may it be aesthetical, moral, traditional, and physical. Philippine folk dances are categorized according to their nature and geographical extent is one of them. Since the Philippines is considered to be an archipelago, aside from farming, fishing is one of the livelihoods of Filipinos living near bodies of water. A type of dance that is anchored to the livelihood of a certain area and displays the customs of folks in the

workplace is called Occupational Dance (Gabao, 2015). In such a type of dance, published or unpublished works support the fact that the Philippines have plenty of dances inspired by the abundance of fishing styles, methods, or techniques used by the Filipinos in their fishing occupation. Some of which are *Kin-naras* in the north, *Panulo* in the Visayan Region, and *Tauti* in the south. Since fishing is practiced around the country, it is not new in the Visayan group of islands. In fact, the province of Badian in Cebu, Philippines practices a style of fishing called "*Dayang-Dayang*". It is a way of fishermen to lure the fishes towards the "*pukot*" (net-trap) through performing various body movements. This form of fishing attracts and entertains the residents in the place since the exaggeration of movement makes the fishermen look like dancing. However, "*Dayang-Dayang*" has not been documented ever since. In fact, Dance Heritage Coalition, Inc. (2006) reported that the

low number of research outputs in dance was greatly influenced by the unavailability of resources which serves as references to positively build a strong foundation of the dance research. This gives dance enthusiasts less interest to pursue their passion. This is due to the fact that people before used oral transmission to teach dances. Domingo (2018) added that the lack of appropriate guidelines and framework can also affect the preservation and propagation process. With that being said, culture's uniqueness and its potential to be a reference in creating a folk dance will not be preserved and may fade through the years.

As cited by Buot (2013), Anderson (1986) explained that dance is the most perishable form of art - it is forever endangered. Hence, the study is conducted to document "*Dayang- Dayang*" fishing as a distinct style of fishing livelihood and an existing form of art that is a significant reference to have a strong foundation folk dancing. The study is also done to recognize *Dayang- Dayang's* uniqueness as a reflection of how *Badianganons* would lure fishes as the source of their sustenance. The study therefore looks into the following:

A. Nature and Background

According to Hofilena (2019) dances in the Philippines can be classified in various ways. Nature of Philippine folk dance according to Dimakiling (2017) includes occupational dances, religious/ ceremonial dance, comic dance, game dance, wedding dance, courtship dance, festival dance, and war dance. In other words, the nature of the dance talks about what was its purpose and the origin of its derivation. While background seeks the details, which identify and describe the significance and historical value of "*Dayang- Dayang*" fishing as well as provides references to literature that supports the topic. It is a vital element, as it provides relevant, factual details that are related to a specific topic (open PR Article). This means that this study will identify the impact of such fishing habits in shaping the culture of *Badianganons* (people of Badian).

B. Characteristics

Characteristics are distinctive features used to separate distinguishable things into categories. Hofilena (2019) categorizes folk dance based on its nature, geographical location, and suites. Occupational dance is one of the classifications anchored to the livelihood of a certain area and group of people. Hence, "*Dayang-*

Dayang" can be classified based on its characteristics, in which it depicts the livelihood of Badianganon which can be incorporated as occupational dance. "*Dayang- Dayang*" is distinctively unique, since only *Badianganons* practice this kind of fishing which looks like a dance.

C. Movement Patterns

According to an article by Woodruff (2003), a movement pattern is a particular succession of muscle activation. Schrader (2005) added that movement patterns are locomotor and non-locomotor motions—whether slow-paced or vigorous – that have something to do with running, jumping, leaping, and walking, and were coined as the basic vocabulary of natural, human movements as well as considered as the building blocks of dance. Aside from that, it is associated also with movement concepts which collectively refers to all movement elements. These are the knowledge and understanding of movements that allows individuals to adapt and modify their movements to achieve specific goals. In assessing movement concepts and patterns, one should focus on these categories: Body (what can the body do?), Space (Where does the body move?), Effort (How does the body move?), and Relationship (With whom or with what does the body move?). This means that movement concepts coupled with movement patterns are used to transport the body from one place in space to another. Therefore, the human body can be used as an instrument to form an art which could be also in a form of dance.

Documenting *Dayang- Dayang* Fishing for it to become a reference in Folk dancing is vital in preserving, conserving, and propagating the heritage and tradition of *Badianganons* (people of Badian). As a matter of fact, strengthening and preserving the culture where folk dances belong to can contribute to cultural awareness which is the foundation of literacy of national communication (Poralan et al, 2012). In relation, Tan & Jimeno (2019) coined that in the context of preserving culture, authenticity plays an important role in ensuring that what has been established and practiced by past generations is not manipulated and altered. However, the advent of modernization makes it difficult. Hence, the study is timely and relevant since it gives importance to the conservation and preservation of the fishing tradition of *Badianganon* (people of Badian), as well as make their fishing tradition a reference for future folk dance that will showcase their way of living. In the same way, it is essential to the researchers themselves and the rest of the

physical education students. This study will contribute to the existing list of dance literatures in the country which serve as stepping-stones and foundation for further dance researches (Dance Heritage Coalition, 2006).

The study is anchored on the following theories: The Theory of Cultural Transmission which highlights the passing of culture and customs from one generation in society to another for awareness and social connectedness to take place. This idea is very vital according to the World Health Organization (2009) as cited by Buot (2013). Aside from that, it is also rooted in George Murdock Theory of Cultural Universal which has something to do with the common existing human culture around the planet that only differs on the interpretation of a certain group, such as values and modes of behavior. Moreover, the study also makes Ritzer's Theory of Sociology (2007) a basis. It is a collection of interrelated ideas that require the social world's knowledge to be systematized. The Grand Theory and Daily Life Theory Orientations are the foundation of this theory. To expound, The Grand Hypothesis is an attempt to deal with culture as a whole to understand the system's nature and the mechanisms of transformation that create human history. On the other hand, in an effort to understand individual behaviors and relationships between persons, as well as views, perceptions, and values within the framework of communities and the larger social system, Daily Life Philosophy reflects on, sometimes mundane, human behavior. This theory looks at the change in terms of development.

With that, an article by Buot (2013) supports the preservation of cultures through creating a video documentation of a certain traditional dance in Leyte, Philippines which shows the everyday life and culture of *Baybayans* (people in Leyte) to revive its history that the younger generations must know. Similar studies have been made that support the feasibility of this dance research. Published research entitled *Mangamaru: A creative indigenous Kapampangan folk dance (Philippine)* by Santos et al. (2015) derives dance from a cultural activity in Pampanga which depicts a lively catching of *Kamaru* – a mole cricket that pests the farmers' rice fields. Aside from that, Limen et al. (2019) in their study also focuses on the giving of awareness of millennials in Cebu regarding the province's culture and folk dances since it is revealed that young ones have low awareness within that matter. Hence, this highlights the reality that the culture should be documented, preserved, propagated, and must be given the importance that it

deserves through creating Folk Dances and Traditional Dances out of it. It is therefore important to conduct an ethnographic study of *Dayang-Dayang* Fishing for Folk Dance Reference to preserve culture and traditions; provide a strong foundation of folkdance research; and to apply methodological frameworks proposed by other researchers.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURES AND STUDIES

Various cultural dance forms in the Philippines mirror the multihued customs and traditions of Filipinos that are noticeable during celebrations, festivals, and other social gatherings. Folk dances and traditional dances are some of them which showcase the Filipinos' way of living and beliefs. Dance therefore has been a part of the lives of the Filipino people. Philippine folk dances are affluent as history itself yet are rarely seen by the new generation (Hofileña, 2019). Studies are conducted with the aim to contrast, document, preserve, and propagate these folk dances to effectively transfer the Filipino heritage to the next generation. With that, various local and international articles, studies, and researches emerged which highlights the sorts of dance literature and cultural dances itself, in the country which findings differ from one another. Amid the difference, it can still serve as a basis in generating knowledge and new ideas in the field of dance.

Dance is a great source of the country's cultural tradition. Dance has been from the dawn of time, a representation of man's movement and impulses as a social creature. Necessitating only the artistic medium with one's own body for certain reasons, requiring no specific ability, dancing has included entire divisions of the population and therefore is a representation of human history more distinctly than any other cultural expression (Buerdon, 2015). Hence, Philippine folk dance is a genre that mainly presents the various cultural expressions around the country. It mainly seeks to showcase traditional dances of the country in its pure and authentic form as well as upgrade cultural values manifesting in various folk dances, may it be aesthetical, moral, and physical (Dimakiling, 2017). Philippine folk dances are classified/categorized according to their nature, purpose, and popularity in which one is called an occupational dance that displays the livelihood and occupation of folks. Gabao (2015) in his article elaborated on the various occupational dances that reflect the lifestyle and everyday work of Filipino. His article is a popular

reference to this classification of dance. In fact, he provides concrete examples of occupational dances that are anchored with farming and fishing since these are the main livelihoods in the country. Aside from that, numbers of dances – published or unpublished – claims that the Philippines have plenty of dances inspired through the abundance of fishing styles, methods, or techniques used by the Filipinos in their fishing occupation because the country is an archipelago and fishing livelihood is rampant.

However, challenges emerge in the field of cultural dances due to the changing of times and generations. In fact, Limen et al. (2019) in their study focuses on the giving of awareness of millennials in Cebu regarding the province's folk dancing since it is revealed that young ones have low awareness within that matter. According to Poralan et al. (2012), strengthening and preserving the culture where folk dances belong to can contribute to the cultural awareness of which is the foundation of literacy of national communication.

There is a need therefore to preserve culture through dance as this reflects the country's identity, making it unique around the world. However, Domingo (2018) reported that one of the challenges in preserving cultural art forms such as dance is the lack of proper guidelines or documentation process in collecting data and organizing it. With that gap, he was also able to formulate his own method of documenting dances which were proposed to be adopted by future researchers to have uniform procedures in their studies. Domingo's framework includes 5 steps that are taken one after the other, meaning one step is a prerequisite in proceeding to the next one.

Laying it on the line, the article by Patrick (2014) evaluates the works and methodologies used by researchers of whom are Francisca Reyes-Aquino, Sally Ann Ness, and Benizalde to bridge the gap in folk dance Documentation from different methodological viewpoints. He added that the three used a variety of methods like ethnography for Aquino, phenomenology for Ness, and practice as research for Benizalde. His study examines the journey of dance from a mere expression of everyday living and beliefs to become a tool for research. Since his study showcases three diverse methodologies, he came to a conclusion that dances with their nature can be examined in different ways that can generate knowledge and awareness out of it. Thus, there are sorts of possibilities to document dances. In fact, Francisca Reyes-Aquino is a concrete representation of

it since it is still popular at present. She has made great contributions to the Philippine folk dance society through her system in presenting dance notations that are reflected in her books. It was recognized as the Aquino system. Many dance researches and documentation adapted her notation wherein it presents the dance in a definitive way such as figures in particular measures. Other authors who study dances and produced their own volumes of Philippine folk dances manifest the Aquino system in its contents and it is what we use and see today (Philippine Performance Archive, 2017).

With this, a lot of studies relating to the preservation of culture through creating, documenting and propagating Folk Dances emerge using different methodologies. The study of Cariaga (2014) utilizes ethnographic methods wherein they use interviews and field observations to the *Yogads* of Isabela. It aims to notate, analyze and document *Yogad* unpublished traditional dances of Isabela, to showcase people's lifestyle and traits, as well as to preserve, to conserve, and to propagate *Yogad tribe* cultural heritage. There is also a dance composition done by Buot (2013) which uses qualitative design and ethnographic approaches. It highlights the move to document and create a *Binaybayon dance* in Baybay City, Leyte for young ones to know and have awareness of the tradition of having a thanksgiving dance for Blessed Immaculate Conception. Moreover, a dance of *Kapampangans* called "*Mangamaru*" which is the focus of Santos et al. (2015) study aims to assess *Kapampangan's* diversity, artistry, and creativity in culture. The researchers utilize a descriptive and partly ethnographic approach in their study to illustrate the dominant cultural ideals of the *Kapampangan* portrayed in the dance which they believe can result in an increased sense of national identity. A publication of Luman-ag et al. (2017) describes the Subanen Dances of '*Banwa'Labo* in Ozamiz City. The study revealed that the legitimacy of all the dances describes and classifies them on the basis of the essential principles and factors influencing folk dances. In addition, the research of Patterson et al. (2018) aims to publish indigenous dances of *Aetas* and present them in a creative or theatrical interpretation. The dances were more on imitative movements from the daily activities of the *Aetas* and animals that interacted with them. The study is descriptive and focuses on the movement patterns of the *Aetas* in making a creative dance to follow the authenticity of the movement. Their outputs were evaluated by dance experts to collect feedback on how to improve the dance. There is also a study of Abarca (2013) which documents the indigenous "*Lumad*" dances

of *Ata-Manobo of Talaingod* in Davao del Norte. The researcher witnesses and involves herself in the tribe community to gather the necessary information to document the tribal dances which depict people's way of living. The purpose of this study is to preserve and document the authenticity of "*Lumad*" dances before it would be influenced and tarnished with new cultural genres. This research study used the descriptive method which involves interviews, focus group discussion, and observations. Furthermore, the journal of Fernando-Amilbansa (2012) reported how the author was able to draw choreography from a certain dance (*Pangalay*) in Sulu without sacrificing the authenticity of the dance through analyzing its intricate movement patterns. It was also highlighted by Namiki (2018) that preserving authentic Maranao dances is a big challenge today as it is affected by modern Islamization.

Aside from the idea of preserving cultures, dances having socio-cultural and traditional influences are great stepping-stones for physical activity engagement and health awareness among people (women, older adults, and subgroups) that are considered to be at risk of inactivity (Jain & Brown, 2001). With that, it can be a practical form of physical activity that can contribute to one's health and well-being (Olvera, 2008). Furthermore, Douka et al. (2019) stated in their study that dance is a form of exercise that is significant in maintaining a positive lifestyle and good health through brain stimulation, as new moves need to be mastered and recalled continuously. Also, Santos et al. (2015) pointed out that creative dances are potentially appropriate for public performance and inclusion in teaching physical education. That is why Mattson & Lundvall (2013) stated that physical education has been including dance as part of the curriculum. Despite the prevailing challenges in dance and culture preservation due to the changing times and the lack of resources that gives dance enthusiasts less interest to pursue their passion, the researchers inarguably sought to conduct this study entitled "Descriptive Study of Badian Fishermen's *Dayang-Dayang* Form of Fishing for Folk Dancing" which aims to preserve culture and traditions (Landaran, n.d.); provide a strong foundation of folk dance research (Dance Heritage Coalition Inc, 2006); and to apply methodological frameworks in preserving dances (Domingo, 2018).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Dance Heritage Coalition, Inc. (2006) reported that the low number of research outputs in dance was greatly influenced by the unavailability of resources which serves as references to positively build a strong foundation of the dance research. With that, as cited in the study of Buot (2013), Anderson (1986) explained that dance is the most perishable form of art - it is forever endangered. Hence, the study is timely and relevant since it gives importance to the conservation and preservation of the fishing tradition of *Badianganon* (people of Badian), the study is conducted to document "*Dayang-Dayang*" fishing as a distinct style of fishing livelihood and an existing form of art that is a significant reference for folk dancing. The study is also done to recognize *Dayang-Dayang's* uniqueness as a reflection of how *Badianganons* would lure fishes as the source of their sustenance. Also, this study will contribute to the existing list of dance literature in the country which serve as stepping-stones and foundation for further dance research (Dance Heritage Coalition, 2006). With that, the study looks into the following: *Nature* (purpose and the origin of its derivation) and *Background* (significance and historical value), *Characteristics* (distinctive features), and *Movement Patterns* (succession of muscle activation).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study utilized qualitative design and descriptive approaches. This is descriptive because this presents and describes the nature and background, characteristics, and movement patterns of "*Dayang-Dayang*" fishing in Badian, Cebu, Philippines. This study aims to gather an in-depth understanding of *Badianganon's* fishing style to come up with a dance literature that is a significant basis for a dance research that originated in the locale. With this design, observations are utilized since it focuses more on what is the subject about rather than how and why (Gall et al. 2007).

Research Environment

The study took place in one of the southern municipalities in Cebu, Philippines – Badian. The place is located at 9.832089 latitude and 123.415926 longitudes. This study emphasizes two *barangays* in the municipality since it is said that these certain fishermen

doing “*dayang-dayang*” fishing performs in the coastal areas of Badian particularly between the mainland and the island *Barangay* of Zaragosa however they are living in the mountainous part of the municipality, in *Barangay Tigbao* which is approximately 6.2 to 13 km. away from the fishing grounds.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The study used purposive sampling since it focuses on one particular group of people who perform “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing in Badian, Cebu. The purposive sampling method is a form of non-probability sampling that is most effective when one needs to research with experts in a certain cultural domain. Thus, “*Dayang-Dayang*” popularity among the *Badianangons* (People in Badian) is undeniable but gathering the information from the people who practice “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing themselves is more reasonable than asking randomly. Researchers sought to set criterias in choosing research participants in order to select cases that help address research questions or achieve research goals. In the 37, 912 population of Badian, Cebu, the researchers agreed to have 15 homogeneous participants, both male and female with the age ranges 18 and above to be interviewed in this study. The act of choosing the sampling size was supported by the study of Guest et al (2006) which states that the saturation phenomenon or known as the time when a researcher is no longer learning very much (if anything) from each subsequent interview and observation, often occurs around 12 participants in homogeneous groups. Aside from that, it was also supported by Crouch & McKenzie (2006) which highlights the idea that less than 20 participants in a qualitative study help a researcher build and maintain a close relationship and thus improve the “open” and “frank” exchange of information. With that, the researchers of this study agreed on having 15 homogeneous participants. The key informants in this qualitative study are mainly the fishermen and their

family members of whom are identified to perform and practice the said fishing style for more than 10 years. This process is done to get raw data that are needed in the study.

Research Instruments

The main instrument used in this study was a structured interview checklist that contains the inquiries about the study for the researchers and participants to be guided during the conduct of the interview. Ideas and concepts that are emphasized in the structured interview checklist are being adapted by the study of Buot (2013) and were also being modified by the researchers for it to be aligned with the aims of the study. Other instruments used include phone cameras and voice recorders. Phone cameras are intended to record and document *Dayang-Dayang* to observe the forms, characteristics, styles, and movement patterns of this kind of fishing. Aside from that, voice recorders are utilized to record the answers of the key informants involved in the study.

Data Collection

One representative of the researchers which is from Badian will administer the structured interview through face to face conversation, following the health protocols. This has been decided since there would be difficulty in going to Badian due to the pandemic. Other researchers then will take part in observing the video recordings of “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing which was provided by the team's representative. Before the occurrence of the proper interview, the key informants undergo a briefing through providing a little introduction and some instructions. The researchers use journal notes as a tool to aid the collection of data from key informants.

Data Analysis

The researchers analyze the data out from the description, observation, and interview of the culture-sharing group. To further make the analysis comprehensive, the researchers make a model that is shown below.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers take into account ethical measures in the conduct of the study. Researchers provided a letter addressing the Office of the Mayor of Badian, Cebu to formally inform and ask permission to conduct the research about the “*Dayang-Dayang*” form of fishing for folk dancing in the municipality. The researchers also provided a letter of consent to the key informants of the study for them to know and affix their consent regarding the study. This will serve as proof of agreement for both researchers and participants. In addition, the researchers did not violate the rights of the participants not to take part in the study since they did not force them. The Letter of Consent also is written in three languages – English, Tagalog and in the Vernacular for the participants to understand the research study. The aforementioned ethical acts are done to ensure openness regarding research information, safety, honesty, and confidentiality between researchers and research informants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. OBSERVATIONS, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

A descriptive narrative analysis derived from the common answers or reactions among the key informants during the interview along with other data from the documentation supplements.

1.1 Nature and Background

According to Hofilena (2019) dances in the Philippines can be classified in various ways. Nature of Philippine folk dance according to Dimakiling (2017) includes occupational dances, religious/ ceremonial dance, comic dance, game dance, wedding dance, courtship dance, festival dance, and war dance. In other words, the nature of the dance talks about what was its purpose and the origin of its derivation. While background seeks the details, which identify and describe the significance and historical value of “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing as well as provides references to literature that supports the topic. It is a vital element, as it provides relevant, factual details that are related to a specific topic (open PR Article).

Dayang-Dayang is a unique fishing style that primarily involves “*sabyag*” (water splashes), “*bundakan*” (forceful steps in the water), “*daganon*” (running in the water), “*hapak*” (beating the water with a stick or throwing stones or sand) in the attempt of luring the fishes towards the “*pukot*” (fishing net). It was performed by a certain family clan of fishermen – Jabanes Clan – from the mountainous barangay of *Tigbao*, which is around 7.2 km, north-east, from the town proper of the Municipality of Badian, Cebu, Philippines as a form of livelihood that gives food and income to the family. The derivation of its name comes from the Visayan word “*Duyan-Duyan*” which means “to swing” or “swinging”. The fishing style originated from fishermen coming from the Municipality of Ronda, Cebu, Philippines which is approximately 28.6 km. away from Badian. It is said that the municipality of Ronda has its own way of performing the fishing form when they come to the coastal area of Badian, Cebu wherein fishermen – both males and females – literally dance while luring the fishes in the tune of “*dayang-dayang*”, a popular dance song – in a language that is unfamiliar to many – that is intentionally being played. The Jabanes Clan from the mountains can clearly see this fishing style performed by Ronda fishermen in the coastal areas of Badian, they got interested and eventually imitated the fishing style. However, in the process, The Jabanes Clan realized that the version of the said fishing form coming from Ronda is time-consuming, where there is a ratio of 1:3 per “*Taktakan*” or “cycle of getting fish”. With that, the Jabanes Clan from Badian came up with their own version of “*dayang-dayang*” fishing that was convenient, faster, and easier for them.

Just like other fishermen, the Jabanes Clan used “*pukot*” (fishing net), “*pataw*” (rubber floaters), “*bahayan*” (Nylons), and “*buklot*” (container) in performing “*dayang-dayang*” fishing. The clan prefers doing “*dayang-dayang*” when the sea water is in low tide, any time of the day, because they can easily move in the water as well as can easily spot the fishes. In the clan, the main performers are the males in the family while the females stay at home since that was what they used to do. For the Jabanes Clan, performing “*dayang-dayang*” is happiness and contentment for them especially when they can fully fill up one pail in a single “*taktakan*” (cycle of getting fish).

1.2 Characteristics

Characteristics are distinctive features used to separate distinguishable things into categories. Hofilena (2019) categorizes folk dance based on its nature, geographical location, and suites. Occupational dance is one of the classifications anchored to the livelihood of a certain area and group of people. Hence, *Dayang-Dayang* can be classified based on its characteristics, in which it depicts the livelihood of *Badianganon* which can be incorporated as occupational dance.

“*Dayang-Dayang*” form of fishing in Badian, Cebu, Philippines makes itself unique from any forms of fishing in the country since the movements are distinct from other practices. Fishermen performing this kind of fishing style are like dancing since they incorporate waving of hands and running in the waters while luring the fishes in the “*pukot*” (fishing net). Performing “*dayang-dayang*” involves two to three fishermen at maximum. They start by walking alongside with each other while holding one “*kawayan*” (bamboo pole) attached to each side of the “*pukot*” (fishing net). Disturbances in the shallow water means there is a presence of fishes for them. As a response, they immediately separate the “*kawayan*” (bamboo pole) that they are holding in an opposite direction simultaneously. As they open the net, the side with “*pamato*” (sinkers) should be facing the direction of where the fishes are and the side with the “*pataw*” (rubber floaters) is at the opposite side. As soon as it is ready, they start to do simultaneous movements of which they are like dancing. These movements are “*sabyag*” (water splashes), “*bundakan*” (forceful steps in the water), “*daganon*” (running in the water), “*hapak*” (beating the water with a stick or throwing stones or sand) directing towards the fishes and lures them to enter the “*pukot*” (fishing net). When majority of the fishes are already in the “*pukot*” (fishing net), they then pulled the “*kawayan*” (bamboo pole) which are attached to each side of the “*pukot*” (fishing net) and try to lift it above, as high as they can, preventing the fishes to move and escape, for the fishermen to easily scope their “*kuha*” (harvest) by their hands or with an aid of any apparatus. That is one “*taktakan*” (cycle of getting fish) for the fishermen. And this usually takes less than a minute, depending on the type of fish they catch (whether it is a slow-swimmer or fast-swimmer).

1.3 Movement Patterns

According to an article by Woodruff (2003), a movement pattern is a particular succession of muscle activation. Schrader (2005) added that Movement patterns are locomotor and non-locomotor motions – whether slow-paced or vigorous – that have something to do with running, jumping, leaping, and walking, and were coined as the basic vocabulary of natural, human movements as well as considered as the building blocks of dance. Aside from that, it is associated also with movement concepts which collectively refers to all movement elements. These are the knowledge and understanding of movements that allows individuals to adapt and modify their movements to achieve specific goals. In assessing movement concepts and patterns, one should focus on these categories: Body (what can the body do?), Space (Where does the body move?), Effort (How does the body move?), and Relationship (With whom or with what does the body move?). This means that movement concepts coupled with movement patterns are used to transport the body from one place in space to another. Therefore, the human body can be used as an instrument to form an art which could be also in a form of dance.

The body concept is the most basic and important of all the movement concepts. This answers the question “what can the body do?”. It focuses on the entire body and its parts. The following are its categories: body parts, body shapes, actions of the body parts and actions of the whole body. In terms of the body concept in “*dayang-dayang*” fishing, the arms and the hands are the primary body parts used to perform “*sabyag*” (water splashes) and “*hapak*” (beating the water with a stick or throwing stones or sand). The legs are as important as the arms and hands too for it is where the fishermen exert their efforts to perform “*bundakan*” (forceful steps in the water), “*daganon*” (running in the water). In terms of body shape, fishermen extend their arms sideways, aiming to make their body wider and have a broader space. They apply force in every action of the body parts. Both their arms swing, and they also walk or run in the sea water. They stretch their arms, swing both of their arms, and balance their body in any inclined angles. Performing “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing involves actions of the whole body such as locomotor, non-locomotor, and manipulative. In line with that, fishermen move their whole body simultaneously, movement of feet while running is also partnered with the movement of hand while holding the “*pukot*” (fishing net) toward the direction of the fishes.

Moreover, the space concept helps someone to become an efficient mover. This answers the question “where does the body move?”. It focuses on the spaces, location, and place on where the body will move. Its categories are as follows: location, direction, level, pathway, plane, and extension. The fishermen performing *Dayang-Dayang* consider self-space and general space in fishing. Self-space in a way that they must be attentive once the fishes are near the “*pukot*” (fishing net) or near them. Thus, they also consider general space, or the space shared by their co-fishermen, on how they can best catch the fishes, considering the area or the space. In terms of direction, the fishermen can run forward or sideways. Low, medium and high are the applicable levels in performing “*Dayang-Dayang*”. With the space as wide as the sea water, they can run or walk in different directions and angles, it can be straight or in a zigzag manner.

Aside from that, there is what we called the effort concept that answers the question “How does the body move?”. It highlights the quality of movement a person does. Its categories include time, force, flow and focus. In “*dayang-dayang*” style of fishing, the focus of the fishermen is directed to the object which are the fishes. The moment where there are many fishes gathered in their “*pukot*” (fishing net), the fishermen raise the (pukot) immediately and they will not wait for other fishes to enter because fishes that are already inside their “*pukot*” (fishing net) might escape. Hence, correct timing is really important. The force exerted by the fishermen in “*dayang-dayang*” is dependent on the actions and kinds of fishes the fishermen will catch. The flow might be aggressive or calm depending on the situation, once the fishes they catch are slow paced then the movements of “*dayang-dayang*” is slow. On the other hand, when the fish they catch are fast paced then the movements of “*Dayang-Dayang*” goes with it.

The last movement concept is the relationship concept which answers the question “with whom or with what does the body move?”. It focuses on the connections that occur when moving of which includes body parts, individuals, groups, rules on how to move or play, objects, boundaries, equipment and aspects of various arts. Its categories are the following: people, position, timing, goal, environment. In the concept of relationship, “*Dayang- Dayang*” is done in pairs but it is not limited to such numbers. However, the key informants prefer in pairs since it is what they have practiced for years. They walk alongside each other looking for a school of fish and then just separate in

preparing the “*pukot*” (fishing net). They move simultaneously and do collaborative actions to successfully lure the fishes towards the “*pukot*” (fishing net). After a single “*taktak*” (cycle of getting fish), both transfer to another location adjacent to the recent one. Therefore, it is dynamic in nature.

2. REFLECTION

Mortari (2015) states that reflection is very essential in a qualitative study since it is utilized to validate the procedures done within the research. Thus, in order to be a competent practitioner of research, one should understand first how to reflect in a deep way through connecting and understanding lived experiences of people, through the art of reflection. The researchers incorporate their overall reflections, learnings and realizations based on their observations, analysis and interpretations (Nature and background, Characteristics and movement patterns of *Dayang-Dayang* Fishing).

2.1 Learnings and Realizations

The Philippines is a nation of islets, every island has a unique way of living, and humans are born to be connected. This is why “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing originated from Ronda, Cebu, and later on, this unique style was adopted and modified by the Jabanes clan, a family of fishermen in Badian. Over the years, this style of fishing has been the way of living of the family as well as their means of occupation. For the Jabanes Clan, “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing is not only a form of occupation for them but, it becomes a part of their lives which brings them joy and contentment.

From literally dancing while doing the fishing, the clan simplified the movements for convenience and to have more “*panaktak*”. They call it “*Duyan- Duyan*” but the term “*Dayang- Dayang*” has become the widely known name of it which makes it famous to the town folks. This version of “*Dayang-Dayang*” became a unique feature of the family compared to the neighboring town’s version with only a few equipment differ. Though it is somehow tiring because it uses more energy, it makes them happy and joyous especially when they can have a big catch in only one “*taktak*”. The only basis for them to perform the fishing is the low tides and not the time of the day. As long as it is possible to do “*Dayang-*

Dayang” in such heights of the tides, they pay no attention to what time it is -- morning, noon or late in the afternoon. Only men from the family are known to perform the fishing style.

The arms, hands, and the legs – generally the body extremities, are the main body parts involved in “*Dayang- Dayang*”. They try to widen their body by extending the arms up and down or in static positions. They also do walking and running, stretching, balance, and throwing of pebbles or sands. Self-space and general space are occupied through moving sideways and forward, levels of the body are found to be in low, medium, and high. While chasing the fishes, they may go straight or zigzag in their paths. Their efforts in doing body movements depends on what type of fishes they are about to catch. If fishes such as the “*gono*” (*Atherinomorus lacunosus*) are their target which has a great agility in the water, their movements also become fast. On the other hand, when it is “*ibis*” (*Ambassis kopsii*) which are relatively slower, the movements of the fishermen become slow or gradual. However, for fishes that accelerate while moving in the sea water, movements become accelerated too for the fishermen. This means that the movements of the fishermen are directly proportional to the speed of the fishes. Usually, “*Dayang- Dayang*” is done in pairs with both walking alongside in search for a school of fishes in the shallow waters. They do simultaneous actions collaboratively to successfully lure fishes towards the fishing net. They move every after one “*taktak*” or even during the process. Therefore, it is dynamic in nature.

With that being said, “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing is indeed unique and distinctive in nature, its beauty in terms of nature and background, characteristics and movement patterns are in need of sharing to the world. From the rich culture of *Badianganon* fishermen, their distinct equipment used while fishing, to their rare way of luring the fishes, all in all deserve to be showcased as a form of art. *Dayang-Dayang* fishing alluring features will then be preserved and performed as an occupational dance that depicts the daily living of *Badianganons*. Hence, through showcasing it to all, “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing incorporated as occupational dance will not be forgotten and will never be endangered to perish.

3. OUTPUT

Dominggo (2018) states that the last phase of dissemination and transformation of a specific folk dance is coined as an output. Output phase undergoes evaluation of the documentation of culture that has been done by the researchers. This study’s output focuses on the Fundamental Dance Steps, Time Signature, Costumes and Props in “*Dayang-Dayang* ” Fishing which are based on the description, observation, and interview of the culture-sharing group – Jabanes Clan in Badian, Cebu Philippines.

3.1 Fundamental Dance Steps

Fundamental Dance steps serve as a basis or “basic” steps that let one’s body to move rhythmically usually to the beat of music (merriam webster). Below are the fundamental dance steps of *Dayang-Dayang*:

Baklay - It is a Visayan term which means “walking”. It is done through the following: raise R(L) knee while the foot is pointed downwards and step forward (ct.1), raise L(R) knee while the foot is pointed downwards and step forward (ct.2). Repeat steps as desired. This step can be done in any direction.

Sabyag - It is a Visayan term which means “water splashes”. It is done through the following: (2 measures) place both arms beside the body facing front while the trunk is bent forward slightly, step R(L) foot forward (ct. 1), straighten up your body and extend your arms upward as if you are splashing water, step L(R) foot in front of the other (ct.2), repeat (ct.1) but do not bent the trunk, repeat (ct. 2).

Daganon - It is a Visayan term which means “running in the water”. It is done through the following: while facing front, step R(L) sideways (ct.1), step L(R) across the front of the R(L) (ct.2), repeat cts. 1 & 2 as desired. Arms are extended sideways while the palms face front.

Bundakan - It is a Visayan term which means “forceful steps”. It is done through the following: raise R(L) knee and stamp foot forward (ct.1), raise L(R) knee and stamp the foot forward (ct.2)

Mag-abog - It is a Visayan term which means “luring or to lure”. This can be performed through the following:

(2/4 time signature): step R(L) foot sideward R(L) and place arms in waist level while the knees are slightly bent(ct.1) raise both arms in the sides and straighten up the knees(ct. and), lower arms in waist level and bend the knees slightly(ct. 2), raise both arms up in the sides and straighten up the knees(ct. and). Repeat steps starting in the left side. Perform one gallop step.

(3/4 time signature): step R(L) foot sideward R(L) and place arms in waist level while the knees are slightly bent (ct.1) raise both arms in the sides and straighten up the knees (ct. 2) lower arms in waist level and bend the knees slightly (ct.3)

3.2 Time Signature

Time Signature is a sign used in music to indicate meter and usually written as a fraction with the bottom number indicating the kind of note used as a unit of time and the top number indicating the number units in each measure. In “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing, the time signature is 2/4 and can also be 3/4 depending on the type and speed of fishes the fishermen are catching. Below is the simple drum pattern of the two time signatures mentioned.

3.3 Costume

According to Merriam-Webster’s Dictionary, costume is an outfit worn to create the appearance characteristic of a particular period, person, place, or thing. Moreover, the relationship between dance and dance costumes is complex and does not simply reflect dance practice in a specific period, but also social behavior and cultural values. In “*Dayang-Dayang*” fishing, the following costumes are being used: Camisa de Chino, Trousers, and slippers.

Camisa de Chino

Trousers

Slippers

3.4 Props

In dance works, including national folk dance, contemporary dance, classical dance, and ballet, etc., props still play an important part, and the implementation skills of props are increasingly paid attention to. Dance props can improve the imaginative power of dance works, represent the inner life of actors, create a traditional stage setting, transform space and time, decorate the color of the stage and enhance the mood of the dance and the rhythm of the dance (Qian, 2015) [27]. The props used in “*Dayang-Dayang*” are as follows: “*pukot*” (fishing net), “*sakayan*” (paddle boat), “*pataw*” (rubber floaters), “*bahayan*” (Nylons), and “*buklot*” (container).

“*pukot*” (fishing net)

“*sakayan*” (paddle boat)

“*pataw*” (rubber floaters)

“*bahayan*” (Nylons)

“buklot”
(container)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Culture is an important asset of a country and dance is a great part of it. Preserving culture and tradition as well as continuing the practices of the Philippine folk dances upgrades the cultural values of the country. Culture plays a huge part in education as well as practicing Philippine folk dances and traditional dances not only plays a huge part in spreading cultural awareness but also garnering individuals to be physically active while embracing local identity. The study implies that local culture is a good source of contributing to the foundation of promoting national identity. Hence, it is concluded that, through looking at the nature and background, characteristics, and movement patterns of “*Dayang-Dayang*”, it reveals important and interesting facts about history – teaching people the custom and way of life of certain ancestors. It has also distinguished characteristics compared to other existing occupational dances which makes it unique from its props to its exaggerated arm and body movements. The effort the fishing style requires when performing is suitable for students to be engaged in physical activity as well as appreciating the dance form while enjoying it. Moreover, the dance could also give students and teachers a chance in experiencing the traditional way of *Badiangaon* fishing and rediscovering cultural roots. With that being said, the ethnographic study of Badian Fishermen’s *Dayang-Dayang* Form of Fishing for Folk Dancing, can become a great basis for the creation of folkdance and *Dayang-Dayang* Fishing style itself has a potential to become an expression of culture and art through dance.

With that, anchored on the results and discussion of the study, it is recommended to choreograph a

folkdance base from the fundamental dance steps, time signature, costumes, and props of *Dayang-Dayang*. Incorporation of music and appropriate musical accompaniment that can be associated with the dance is highly suggested also. “*Dayang-Dayang*” has a great potential to become an occupational dance for it serves as a mark and identity of rich culture depicting the daily livelihood of *Badianganons*.

APPENDIX

APPENDIX A: CHECKLIST AND GUIDE QUESTIONS FOR INTERVIEW

Nature and Background

- What is Dayang-Dayang Fishing?
- What is the purpose of Dayang- Dayang form of fishing?
- What is the origin of Dayang-Dayang’s derivation?
- What is the significance and historical value of Dayang- Dayang fishing?
- What is the equipment used for Dayang-dayang fishing?
- What do you feel while performing Dayang-Dayang?
- What time of the day do you usually perform Dayang-Dayang? Why?
- In Dayang-Dayang fishing, who performs better man or woman?

Characteristics

- What are the distinctive features of Dayang-Dayang that you can say that makes it separately distinguishable and unique from other fishing practices?
 - A. Movements
 - B. Style
 - C. Equipment
 - D. Rhythm

Movement Patterns

- What are the movement patterns of Dayang-Dayang?

A. Body Concept

1. Body Part
2. Body Shape
3. Action of body part
4. Actions of the whole body

Concepts	Categories and subcategories	Movement elements					
Body	Body parts	Head, neck, ears, eyes, nose, mouth, shoulders, elbows, wrists, hands, fingers, belly, chest, spine, back, bottom, hips, knees, ankles, feet, and toes					
	Body shapes	Narrow, wide, round, twisted*, symmetrical, and asymmetrical					
	Actions of body parts	Weight bearing, receive force or weight, apply force, lead the action, and weight transfer					
	Actions of the whole body	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Nonlocomotor</td> <td>Stretch, curl, twist*, turn, spin, swing, push, pull, rise, sink, gesture, dodge, balance, counterbalance, and countertension</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Locomotor</td> <td>Walk, cartwheel, crawl, bear walk, crab walk, run, leap, hop, skip, jump, gallop, slide, rock, and roll**</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Manipulative</td> <td>Throw, roll***, strike, kick, volley, catch, trap, dribble, and carry</td> </tr> </table>	Nonlocomotor	Stretch, curl, twist*, turn, spin, swing, push, pull, rise, sink, gesture, dodge, balance, counterbalance, and countertension	Locomotor	Walk, cartwheel, crawl, bear walk, crab walk, run, leap, hop, skip, jump, gallop, slide, rock, and roll**	Manipulative
Nonlocomotor	Stretch, curl, twist*, turn, spin, swing, push, pull, rise, sink, gesture, dodge, balance, counterbalance, and countertension						
Locomotor	Walk, cartwheel, crawl, bear walk, crab walk, run, leap, hop, skip, jump, gallop, slide, rock, and roll**						
Manipulative	Throw, roll***, strike, kick, volley, catch, trap, dribble, and carry						

Relationship	People	Solo, alone in a mass, partners, even groups, uneven groups, individual to group, group to group, triangle, circle, square, scattered, spokes of a wheel, and X	
	Position	Above/below, over/under, inverted, mount/dismount, in front of/behind, beside, alongside, through, surround, around, support/supported, lift/lifted, meet/part, and near to/far from	
	Timing	Simultaneous	Mirror, match, contrast, and unison
		Alternate	Take turns
		Successive	Movement sequence, canon, question/answer, act/react, and lead/follow
Goal	Cooperative, collaborative, and competitive		
Environment	Static and dynamic		

B. Space Concept

1. Location
2. Direction
3. Level
4. Pathway
5. Plane
6. Extension

Space	Location	Self-space and general space
	Direction	Forward, backward, sideways, up, down, clockwise, and counterclockwise
	Level	Low, medium, high
	Pathway	Straight, curved, and zigzag
	Plane	Sagittal, frontal, and transverse
	Extension	Small and large

C. Effort Concept

1. Time
2. Force
3. Flow
4. Focus

Effort	Time	Fast, slow, and acceleration
	Force	Hard and soft
	Flow	Bound and free
	Focus	Direct and indirect

D. Relationship Concept

1. People
2. Position
3. Timing
4. Goal
5. Environment

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